

DEVELOPMENT OF OPERATIONAL VISUAL THINKING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SKILLS IN SECONDARY MEDICAL PERSONNEL

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Abstract: We are all witnessing that the reforms in the medicine of our country are being continued at a new stage and huge positive changes are taking place. The activity of the training system plays an important role in the timely performance of the tasks set before the representatives of the field by the head of our state, and in the further improvement of the quality of medical services provided to our people.

Key words: skill, thinking, field, medicine, training, system.

PF of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 7, 2017 Decision No. 4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017 "On Measures for the Further Development of the Higher Education System" No. 4947 is a huge task for the educational system and 173 took responsibility. In the fourth priority direction of the action strategy, special emphasis is placed on the development of the social sphere, and Uzbekistan, which has set itself the goal of becoming one of the developed countries, has made it a priority to introduce advanced technologies in the field of education, as well as in all sectors of the national economy, and thereby bring the content of education to the level of world standards. was determined.

In such conditions, the demands for highly qualified pedagogues are increasing, and they have the ability to educate the young generation in the spirit of universal and national values that have been formed for centuries.

It is necessary to form highly qualified creative and cultured pedagogues who have thoroughly mastered the fundamentals of science, are deeply armed with pedagogic and psychological methods, have a high level of medical training, and have mastered modern pedagogical and information technologies.

An innovative approach to the educational process educates students in the development of a desire to acquire new experiences, creativity and critical thinking, and a hopeful outlook on the future. It is appropriate to conduct training using innovative educational methods in the organization of the educational process in network centers for the retraining of pedagogic personnel and their qualification improvement.

It's no secret to us that the majority of students who come to retraining and professional development are professors and teachers with scientific competence and many years of work experience.

It is traditional to teach such potential professors the use of educational methods does not correspond to the current era. Also, it will not be possible to activate and interest all the listeners in the classes organized on the basis of traditional educational methods. Based on this, it is appropriate for every teacher who teaches in the training course to use various interactive educational methods that interest and activate students based on the content of the taught module.

Currently, there are more than a thousand interactive educational methods in Uzbekistan is used in the educational process. This does not mean that all interactive learning methods can be used in all classes. Educational methods are selected based on the criteria for choosing educational methods: Criteria for choosing educational methods According to the didactic task According to the possibilities and number of students According to the material and technical conditions According to the allocated time According to the skills of the teacher According to the didactic task The purpose of the subject, the expected results, the lesson it also depends on the type, form of the lesson and the content of the educational material and the complexity of the subject.

Depending on the capacity and number of learners, psychological characteristics of learners, knowledge levels and, of course, the number of learners. When it comes to the number of learners

there are methods that require that the number of learners and the number of subgroups be the same.

The duration of education means the duration of the topics of the educational module, of course, affects the choice of method. The training period may be so limited that the time-consuming method does not allow you to use it as often as you would like. Therefore, depending on the content of the topics, if the topic is complex, easy, fast and time-consuming methods can be used, if the content of the topic is closely related to the previous topics, complex and time-consuming methods can be used.

Educational-material technical conditions require handouts, colored papers, flipchart papers, pinboards, magnets, markers, scotch tape, scissors and scissors when we use interactive methods. It is self-evident that the skill of the teacher means that you should be able to choose the most appropriate methods in the

educational process. The teacher's ability to choose methods correctly shows his level of methodological competence.

The teacher should have the ability to ask the right questions and master the question-and-answer technique. In addition, the teacher should know how to summarize feedback and draw conclusions when using non-traditional methods, and also have the ability to manage a group. If professors and teachers teaching in training centers choose these educational methods based on the criteria for choosing interactive methods, students' interest and activity in the subject will increase and their attitude to training will change.

The passing modules are easily, quickly and effectively mastered by them is brought

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